

README FILE

Project Structure

data/ :

- Contains input datasets used by the simulation.
- Files include battery demand and supply data, raw material statistics, and other relevant information.

modules/

Core Python modules for the simulation:

- `Demand.py` : Battery demand calculations.
- `Supply.py` : Battery supply calculations.
- `SupplyReverse.py` : Calculations to estimate achievable BEV shares with only domestic batteries.
- `RawMaterials.py` : Raw material requirement estimations.
- `Save.py` : Handles saving intermediate and final simulation results.
- `Plotter.py` : Generates plots for visualizing results.

plots/

- `jpg/`: Folders for storing output plots in JPEG formats.
- `pdf/`: Folders for storing output plots in PDF formats.
- plots are created via `Plotter.py` or `plotter_ scripts`

results/

- `dataFiles/`: Contains saved results from simulations in `.pickle` format.

`main.py` Entry point for the simulation. Configurable parameters and the simulation workflow are defined here.

Running the Simulation

The simulation is started and controlled from `main.py`. The key parameters and workflow are:

1. Initialization:

Modules for demand, supply, reverse supply, raw materials, and saving are initialized.

2. Configuration Options

- Prediction Mode (`modePP`): Choose between "PERT" (default) or "TruncNorm".
- Curve Fit Diffusion Model (`modeCF`): Choose from "LOG" (default), "GOM", or "BASS".
- Supply Adjustment (`modeS`): Options:
 - None (default)
 - "limGR" (limit growth rate)
 - "woOEE" (ignore utilization / OEE)
 - "limGR_woOEE" (Only compatible with "LOG" and "GOM".)
- Save Results (`saveMode`): True to save results after each simulation, False to skip saving.
- Iterations (`N_MonteCarlo`): Set the number of Monte Carlo simulation iterations.

3. Simulation Workflow

- Predict demand and supply.
- Check the validity of the model fit.
- Calculate raw material requirements and BEV shares
- Save and combine results.
- Generate plots at the end of the simulation.

Start the Simulation

Edit the configuration options in `main.py` as required and run:

```
python main.py
```

Example Configuration in `main.py`

- `modePP` = "PERT" ("PERT" or "TruncNorm")
- `modeCF` = "LOG" ("LOG", "GOM", "BASS")
- `modeS` = None ("limGR", "woOEE", "limGR_woOEE")
- `saveMode` = False (SAVE (=TRUE) or NO SAVE (FALSE))
- `N_MonteCarlo` = 10 (NUMBER OF ITERATIONS)

Outputs

Simulation results and visualizations are saved in the following locations:

- Data Files: `results/` (Pickle format)
- Plots: `plots/jpg/` and `plots/pdf/`

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European Battery Demand

European Battery Cell Production

European Raw Material Demand

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Authors and acknowledgment

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